

Variability of Direct Seeded Rice Cultivars in Growth, Productivity and Kernel Quality under Different Seeding Depths

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ABSTRACT

Optimum seeding depth is essential to attain the maximum production potential of a cultivar. To examine the effect of various planting depths in coarse and fine aromatic rice under direct seeding, pot and field studies were executed at University of Agriculture, Faisalabad during kharif 2012. Experiment was comprised of two rice cultivars viz., super basmati (fine aromatic rice) and KSK-133 (coarse rice) which were sown at various seeding depths viz., 2, 3, 4 and 5 cm using randomized complete block design (RCBD) under factorial arrangement of treatments replicated three times. Results indicated that stand establishment attributes were statistically affected by seeding depth. Increasing seeding depth resulted in low performance of all the yield related parameters. At seeding depth of 3 cm, leaf area indices, leaf area duration, crop growth rate, total dry matter accumulation and net assimilation rate of coarse and fine rice were improved. Likewise, significantly higher yield and its related components were recorded, when crop was sown at seeding depth of 3 cm. This treatment furnished kernel yields of 5.08 and 4.23 t ha⁻¹ in coarse and fine aromatic rice, respectively, which were significantly higher than rest of treatments. Furthermore, at same depth kernel quality was also improved in terms of lower number of sterile, opaque and chalky kernels. Nonetheless, Water absorption ratio was also higher in these kernels. As for kernels protein content concerned it was decreased with increasing seeding depth. It is concluded that sowing at seeding depth of 3 cm for direct seeded coarse and fine rice cultivars is beneficial in terms of better stand establishment, normal growth, higher yield and improved quality of rice crop.

Key words: Cultivar, direct seeding, growth, productivity, seeding depth

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is the worlds' most important staple food and potentially an important source of energy for people who eat mainly rice. It is cultivated in more than 100 countries, mainly in Asia [1]. In rice production Asia is the leader and it accounts above 90% of world rice production [2]. Rice being worldwide important cash crop holds a distinctive status in Pakistan's agriculture. It is the 2nd major staple food crop after wheat and 3rd largest cash crop after Heaven food (wheat) and Silver gold (cotton) in Pakistan. It is the main economic crop and its export accounted for 1% of GDP and 4.9% of value added in agriculture. Currently, Pakistan is growing rice on an area of 2.57 m ha with an average yield of 2.4 t ha⁻¹ [3]. Conventionally, rice is sown in puddled soils by transplanting 25-35 days old seedlings from wet nurseries of rice. Puddling method also affects the soil health by sorting out of particles of soil that results in soil compaction and on the other hand, improper seedbed preparation, inefficiency in input management, less plant population, late transplanting and shortage of labor during the peak transplanting time, high water losses occur during puddling process through seepage and by ground evaporation, shortage of irrigation water supply and

drainage facilities are drawbacks of rice transplanting method [4, 5, 6]. Direct seeded rice (DSR) is an alternative of puddling method in rice cultivation which gives higher economic returns, DSR is faster and easier to plant, less labor and water resources consumed less effort for sowing the same area [7]. It requires less water, resources, farm inputs and labor. Transplanted rice plants mature late (7-10 days) than direct seeded rice, so timely sowing of next crop which is wheat becomes possible [7, 8, 9]. In direct seeding less than 44% of water can be used as compared to conventional transplanted system by reducing leakage, seepage and evaporation losses, while maintaining an adequate level of production or yield [10].

Copeland and McDonald [11] stated that the yield gap (50-60%) between potential and actual yield at farmer's field is attributed to several agronomic constraints like soil physical properties, land preparation, seed viability, genotypic characteristics and seeding depth. Sadras and Calvino [12] indicated that improper seed placement leads to poor root establishment which often results in reduction of water and nutrient use efficiency. Seeds sown at greater depth remain ungerminated or seedlings remain unable to come out of the soil surface due to compaction, seedling vigor, soil porosity or soil

texture [13]. To find out the optimum seed depth of any crop is crucial in this regard, as it provides the base for better crop establishment. Depth of seed placement varies among crops as well as cultivars. Bold seeded crop require more sowing depth than small seeded crops. Similarly, genotypic differences exist for their response to different sowing depths. Keeping in mind the above facts, this study was conducted to identify the optimum seeding depths on growth, productivity and quality of coarse and fine aromatic rice.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

For growth, yield and quality attributes of two direct seeded rice cultivars under various seeding depths, a field experiment was conducted at Agronomic Research Area, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad (73.09°E longitude, 31.25°N latitude, 184 m above sea level) during 2012. Experimental treatments comprised of two rice cultivars (Super Basmati and KSK-133) and four seeding depths (2, 3, 4 and 5cm). The experiment was laid out in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with factorial arrangement having three replications and net plot size was maintained 2.0 m × 6.0 m. Seeds were soaked in water for 24 hours prior to seeding for better germination and stand establishment. Treated seeds were dibbled in saturated soil in 20 cm spaced rows with a single row hand drill on June 14, 2012. A fertilizer dose of 100-67-62 kg NPK ha⁻¹ in the form of Urea, DAP and MOP, respectively was applied. Whole quantity of DAP and MOP with 1/3rd part of urea was applied prior to seeding as basal dose while the remaining of nitrogen divided in two splits and applied at two critical stages as tillering and panicle initiation. Irrigation was applied when the soil reached at field capacity level. For weed control, mixture of Ethoxysulphuran (Sunstar 15 WG) and Phenoxyprop-p-ethyle (Puma Super 7.5 EW) @ 200 g and 370 ml ha⁻¹ respectively was applied and manual weeding was also done at regular intervals in soil. Carbofuran (Furadan 3G) was broadcasted @ 25 kg ha⁻¹ to protect the crop from stem borers and leaf folders. Data regarding growth parameters (leaf area index, leaf area duration, crop growth rate, net assimilation rate and total dry matter accumulation), yield related components (plant Height, total tillers, productive tillers, unproductive tillers, panicle length, no. of branches per panicle, no. of kernels per panicle, 1000 kernel weight, kernel yield, straw yield, biological yield, harvest index) and quality parameters (sterile kernels, opaque kernels, abortive kernel, chalky kernels, normal kernels, kernel length, kernel width, kernel protein content and water absorption ratio) were recorded using standard procedures and collected data was analyzed statistically by using Fisher's analysis of variance technique and significant means were separated using least significant difference (LSD) test at 5% probability level [14].

3. RESULTS

3.1 Plant Growth and Development Attributes

Leaf area index was substantially improved and was observed maximum during middle of growth period but that was then decreased when crop reached towards maturity. This trend was similar for both cultivars. In KSK-133 LAI was higher at a seeding depth of D₂. Same trend was observed in Super Basmati at seeding depth of D₂ (Figure 1). In cultivar Super Basmati LAD was higher at a seeding depth of D₂ followed by

D₃ (Figure 2). Same trend was observed in KSK-133 at a seeding depth of 3 cm. The minimum LAD was observed at depth of D₄ in both rice cultivars. In cultivar Super Basmati, during initial developmental events, CGR was almost similar to all seeding depth treatments except the D₄ seeding depth which exhibited less CGR than D₂ (Figure 3). Similar trend was observed in other cultivar KSK-133. The minimum CGR was observed at depth of D₄ in both rice cultivars. The net photosynthates produced by a crop per unit leaf area duration are represented by net assimilation rate. Net assimilation rate (NAR) was significantly improved at a seeding depth of D₃ as compared to others (Figure 4). Maximum NAR was recorded at a seeding depth of D₃ followed by D₄ in Super Basmati while in KSK-133 maximum NAR was recorded at a seeding depth of D₄ followed by D₃. Whereas minimum NAR was observed at a seeding depth of D₁ in both rice cultivars. In cultivar Super Basmati, TDM was higher at a seeding depth of D₂ followed by D₃ (Figure 5). In KSK-133, same trend was observed at seeding depth of D₂. The minimum TDM was observed at seeding depth of D₄ in both rice cultivars.

Figure 1. Leaf area index (LAI) as influenced by various seeding depths in direct seeded two rice cultivars (A) Super basmati (B) KSK-133. Vertical bars above mean denote standard error of three replicates.

Figure 2. Leaf area duration (LAD) as influenced by various seeding depths in direct seeded two rice cultivars (A) Super basmati (B) KSK-133. Vertical bars above mean denote standard error of three replicates.

Figure 3. Crop growth rate (CGR) as influenced by various seeding depths in direct seeded two rice cultivars (A) Super basmati (B) KSK-133. Vertical bars above mean denote standard error of three replicates.

Figure 4. Net assimilation rate (NAR) as influenced by various seeding depths in direct seeded two rice cultivars (A) Super basmati (B) KSK-133. Vertical bars above mean denote standard error of three replicates.

Figure 5. Total dry matter accumulation (TDM) as influenced by various seeding depths in direct seeded two rice cultivars (A) Super basmati (B) KSK-133. Vertical bars above mean denote standard error of three replicates.

3.2 Agronomic Traits

All agronomic parameters influenced significantly by various seeding depth treatments in both rice cultivars excepting unproductive tillers (Table 1 & 2). Plant height statistically differed among various seeding depths treatments. Maximum plant height (77.04 cm) was noted at a seeding depth of D₂ in both rice cultivars. Minimum plant height (80.48 cm) and (54.36 cm) was observed at a seeding depth of D₄ for Super Basmati and KSK-133, respectively. Total tillers are statistically differed among seeding depths treatments as represented in. Super Basmati produced more tillers as compared with KSK-133. Among seeding depth treatments maximum number of tillers (380.33) for KSK-133 while (395.67) for Super Basmati at seeding depth of D₂ was produced. Among rice cultivars maximum total number of tillers (375.42) was produced in Super Basmati and minimum total number of tillers (364.08) was produced in KSK-133. Different seeding depth treatments significantly affected the productive tillers of rice cultivars. KSK-133 produced more productive tillers as compared with Super Basmati. Among seeding depth treatments maximum productive tillers (377.67) for Super Basmati while (357.67) for KSK-133 at seeding depth of D₂ were produced. Minimum total numbers of tillers (337.87) were produced at a seeding depth of D₄. Between two rice cultivars maximum productive tillers (358.08) were produced in Super Basmati and minimum total numbers of tillers (346.92) were produced in KSK-133. The data showed that seeding depth treatments gave non-significant results for

unproductive tillers of rice. Number of unproductive tillers (m⁻²) ranged from 11.33 to 14.33 in KSK-133 while 15.33 to 20.67 in Super Basmati. The cultivars showed non-significant results with different seeding depth treatments. The Super Basmati rice cultivar showed the more number of unproductive tillers per m² (17.33) as compared to KSK-133 (17.16). Maximum panicle length (22.06 cm) was noted when seeds were placed at a D₂ depth in both rice cultivars. Minimum panicle length 19.28 cm was observed when seeds were placed at D₄ depth in both rice cultivars. Among rice cultivars maximum panicle length (21.54 cm) was observed in Super Basmati. Different seeding depth treatments affected significantly branches per panicle of both rice cultivars. However, rice cultivars were not significant for branches per panicle. Maximum number of branches per panicle (9.33) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₂. Minimum number of branches per panicle (7.00) was observed at a seeding depth of D₄. Number of kernels per panicle is considered as actual economic yield in rice crop as more number of kernels per panicle will return more yield. Different seeding depth treatments and rice cultivars affected significantly the kernels per panicle. Maximum number of kernels per panicle (76.50) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₂ and it was at par with D₃. While, minimum number of kernels per panicle (61.16) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₄. Among rice cultivars maximum number of kernels per panicle (71.25) was observed in Super Basmati. Maximum 1000-kernel weight (21.66 g) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₂ while minimum 1000-kernel weight (19.58 g) for seeding depth of D₄. Among rice cultivars maximum 1000-kernel weight (21.21 g) was recorded in KSK-133 and minimum 1000-kernel weight (19.98 g) was recorded in Super Basmati (Table 3). Maximum kernel yield (4.65 t ha⁻¹) was recorded at a seeding depth of 3 cm while minimum kernel yield (3.02 t ha⁻¹) at 4 cm. Among rice cultivars maximum kernel yield (4.25 t ha⁻¹) was observed in KSK-133 while minimum kernel yield (3.54 t ha⁻¹) was recorded in Super Basmati. Regarding straw yield, it was maximum (7.08 t ha⁻¹) at a seeding depth of D₂ while minimum straw yield (5.86 t ha⁻¹) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₁. Among rice cultivars maximum straw yield (6.65 t ha⁻¹) was observed in KSK-133 while minimum straw yield (6.35 t ha⁻¹) was noted in Super Basmati. Analysis of variance indicated that different seeding depth treatments significantly affected the biological yield of rice cultivars. Maximum biological yield (11.10 t ha⁻¹) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₂. Minimum biological yield (9.59 t ha⁻¹) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₄. Among rice cultivars maximum biological yield (10.91 t ha⁻¹) was observed in KSK-133 while minimum biological yield (9.85 t ha⁻¹) was noted in Super Basmati. Maximum harvest index (41.85%) was observed at a seeding depth of D₂. Minimum harvest index (31.31%) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₄. Among rice cultivars maximum harvest index (38.69%) was revealed by KSK-133 and minimum harvest index (35.76%) was recorded in Super Basmati.

3.3 Kernel Quality

Various seeding depths had significant effect on all quality related attributes of rice kernels except kernel width and water absorption ratio (Table 3). Seeding depth significantly affected the sterile, opaque, abortive, chalky and normal kernels of rice cultivars. Maximum sterile spikelets (7.63%) were recorded at

a seeding depth of D₄. Among rice cultivars maximum sterile spikelets (7.80%) were observed in KSK-133 while minimum sterile spikelets (5.42%) were noted in Super Basmati. Different seeding depth treatments significantly affected the opaque kernels of rice cultivars. Maximum opaque kernels (8.22%) were recorded at a seeding depth of D₄. Minimum opaque kernels (6.52%) were recorded at a seeding depth of D₂. Among rice cultivars maximum opaque kernels (8.33%) were observed in KSK-133 while minimum opaque kernels (6.97%) were noted in Super Basmati. Maximum abortive kernels (5.19%) were recorded at a seeding depth of D₄. Minimum abortive kernels (3.20%) were recorded at a seeding depth of D₂. Maximum chalky kernels (19.20%) were recorded at a seeding depth of D₄. Minimum chalky kernels (15.18%) were recorded at a seeding depth of D₂. Among rice cultivars maximum chalky kernels (17.83%) were observed in KSK-133 while minimum chalky kernels (16.75%) were noted in Super Basmati. Maximum normal kernels (63.05%) were recorded at a seeding depth of D₂ and minimum (57.66%) at D₄. Among rice cultivars maximum normal kernels (61.02%) were observed in Super Basmati while minimum normal kernels (59.14%) were noted in KSK-133. Longer the kernels higher will be the kernel quality and vice versa. Kernel length was also

significantly affected by seeding depth treatments. Maximum kernel length (5.83 mm) was recorded at seeding depth of D₂ while minimum kernel length (5.77 mm) at D₄. Among rice cultivars maximum kernel length (6.25 mm) was observed in Super Basmati while minimum kernel length (5.35 mm) was noted in KSK-133. Various seeding depth treatments showed non-significant behavior for the kernel width of rice. Rice cultivars were significant for kernel width. In rice cultivars maximum kernel width (1.52 mm) was observed in KSK-133 while minimum kernel width (1.45 mm) was noted in Super Basmati. Rice cultivars were significant for kernel water absorption ratio. Among rice cultivars maximum kernel water absorption ratio (3.39) was observed in Super Basmati while minimum kernel water absorption ratio (3.11) was noted in KSK-133. Different seeding depth treatments significantly affected the kernel protein content of rice. Similarly, rice cultivars were also significant for kernel protein content. Maximum kernel protein content (9.01%) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₁. Minimum kernel protein content (7.65%) was recorded at a seeding depth of D₄. Among rice cultivars maximum kernel protein content (8.67%) was observed in Super Basmati while minimum kernel protein content (8.28%) was noted in KSK-133.

Table 1: Influence of various seeding depths on yield attributes of two rice cultivars in direct seeding

Treatments	PH (cm)	TT (m ⁻²)	PT (m ⁻²)	UPT(m ²)	PL (cm)	NBBPP	NKPP
Seeding depth (cm)							
D ₁ = 2 cm	72.55b	365.00 b	349.00 b	16	20.67 b	8.17 b	65.83 b
D ₂ = 3 cm	77.04 a	388.00a	367.67 a	20.33	22.06 a	9.33 a	76.50 a
D ₃ = 4 cm	74.17ab	373.33 b	355.50 b	17.83	21.16 ab	8.33 ab	75.33 a
D ₄ = 5 cm	67.41 c	352.67 c	337.83	14.83	19.28 c	7.00 c	61.16 c
LSD (P≤0.05)	3.75	10.16	9.70	NS	1.00	0.77	3.82
Rice cultivars							
C ₁ = Super Basmati	86.57 a	375.42 a	358.08 a	17.33	21.54 a	8.41	71.25 a
C ₂ = KSK-133	59.02 b	364.08 b	346.92 b	17.16	20.04 b	8.00	68.16 b
LSD (P≤0.05)	2.65	7.08	6.86	NS	0.71	NS	2.70

PH: Plant Height; TT: Total Tillers; PT: Productive Tillers; UPT: Unproductive Tillers; PL: Panicle Length; NBPP: No. of branches per panicle; NKPP: No. of kernels per panicle

* Any two means not sharing a letter in common within a column differ significantly at 5% probability level by LSD test.

Table 2: Influence of various seeding depths on yield attributes of two rice cultivars in direct seeding

Treatments	1000 KW (g)	KY (t ha ⁻¹)	SY(t ha ⁻¹)	BY(t ha ⁻¹)	HI (%)
Seeding depth (cm)					
D ₁ = 2 cm	20.35 b	3.65 c	5.86 c	10.19 c	35.90 b
D ₂ = 3 cm	21.66 a	4.65 a	7.08 a	11.10 a	41.85 a
D ₃ = 4 cm	20.81 b	4.25 b	6.64 b	10.61 b	39.85 a
D ₄ = 5 cm	19.58 c	3.02 d	6.41 b	9.59 d	31.31 c
LSD (P≤0.05)	0.49	0.32	0.41	0.29	3.00
Rice cultivars					

C ₁ =Super Basmati	19.98 b	3.54 b	6.35 b	9.85 b	35.76 b
C ₂ = KSK-133	21.21 a	4.25 a	6.65 a	10.91 a	38.69 a
LSD (P<0.05)	0.69	0.23	0.29	0.21	2.12

1000 KW: 1000 kernel weight; KY: Kernel Yield; SY: Straw Yield; BY: Biological Yield; HI: Harvest Index;

* Any two means not sharing a letter in common within a column differ significantly at 5% probability level by LSD test.

Table 3: Influence of various seeding depths on grain quality of two rice cultivars in direct seeding

Treatments	SK (%)	OK (%)	AK (%)	CK (%)	NK (%)	KL(mm)	KW (mm)	KPC (%)	WAR (%)
Seeding depth (cm)									
D ₁ = 2 cm	6.85 b	7.99 a	4.18 b	19.99 b	59.09 bc	5.78 ab	1.48	9.01 a	3.24
D ₂ = 3 cm	5.49 c	6.58 b	3.20 d	15.18 d	63.05 a	5.83 a	1.48	8.79 ab	3.27
D ₃ = 4 cm	6.49 b	7.81 a	3.83 c	16.78 c	60.49 b	5.82 ab	1.49	8.48 b	3.26
D ₄ = 5 cm	7.63 a	8.22 a	5.19 a	19.20 a	57.67 c	5.77 b	1.48	7.65c	3.24
LSD (P<0.05)	0.41	0.73	0.26	1.10	1.94	0.06	NS	0.50	NS
Rice cultivars									
C ₁ =Super Basmati	5.42 b	6.97 b	4.11	16.75 b	61.02 a	6.25 a	1.45 b	8.67 a	3.39 a
C ₂ = KSK-133	7.80 a	8.33 a	4.09	17.83 a	59.14 b	5.35 b	1.52 a	8.28 b	3.11 b
LSD (P<0.05)	0.29	0.51	NS	0.78	1.38	0.04	0.05	0.36	0.05

SK: Sterile kernels; OK: Opaque kernels; AK: Abortive kernel; CK: Chalky kernels; NK: Normal kernels; KL: Kernel Length; KW: Kernel width; KPC: Kernel Protein content; WAR: Water absorption ratio

* Any two means not sharing a letter in common within a column differ significantly at 5% probability level by LSD test.

4. DISCUSSION

Seeding depth in both rice cultivars impaired with growth, yield and kernel quality parameters. In our study, higher LAI in D₂ might be attributed to vigorous and healthy crop stand in this treatment. The rice crop at higher seeding depths was poor and weak, due to poor seedlings which could not attain higher LAI. More LAD in D₂ treatment might be because of higher leaf area indices in these plots. The crop stand at this seeding depth was healthy and more vigorous than rest of treatments thus attaining more LAI and ultimately leaf area duration. Higher crop growth rate in D₂ might be attributed to optimal growth conditions that led to dynamic crop stand. This was not in case of other treatments. Genotypic variation regarding growth rate is due to varying morphology and stature of crop plants. Higher NAR in Super Basmati is attributed to higher dry matter accumulation in these plots as compared to KSK-133. Maximum NAR is due to the minimum value of LAD and vice versa. Higher TDM at the seeding depth of D₂ was attributed to better and healthy stand of rice. The KSK-133 produced lower TDM as compared to Super Basmati because it had short stature. Aikins *et al.* [15] also reported more TDM at optimum seeding depth of soybean crop.

Reduction in plant height at D₁ might be due to deficit of soil moisture on the upper layer of soil while at seeding depth of D₄ smaller plants might be because of seed placement at higher depths that prevented the seedlings to emerge from thick soil layer. These results are in line with [15] who reported that deep sowing in cowpea perhaps prevented the seedlings from approaching their shoots above through the bulky soil layer initially leaving the other treatments to get better the opportunity to start faster. Among the cultivars difference may

be due to genetic variation of rice cultivars. The greater number of tillers (m⁻²) in D₂ might be attributed to optimum plant population due to better stand establishment as compared to rest of the treatments in direct sown rice. It might also be due to rich root system that provides essential nutrients to plant that result in vigorous and healthy growth. Reduction in number of tillers (m⁻²) at shallow and deeper depth is might be due to poor root system and poor stand establishment. Rebetkze *et al.* [13] also reported that maximum tillers were produced when crop was sown at optimum seeding depth. Regarding greater number of productive tillers m⁻² in D₂ might be attributed to optimum plant population as compared to rest to treatments in direct-sown rice. It might also be due to rich root system that provides essential nutrients to plant that result in vigorous and healthy growth. Reduction in number of productive tillers m⁻² at shallow and deeper depth was because of poor root system and poor stand establishment. These results were in line with [13] who reported that less productive tillers were produced under deep sowing due to the insufficient stand. The number of tillers without panicles is a yield reducing parameter. Non-productive tillers are produced due to lack of essential plant nutrients at proper timing, environment stress and inter plant competition. Maximum unproductive tiller at D₄ were might be due to poor root system. The plants were unable to take proper nutrients and at shallow depth might be due to non-availability of proper moisture because upper layer of soil dried quickly. More panicle length recorded for D₂ might be due to better stand establishment, vigorous growth and optimal number of productive tillers which resulted in better development of panicle. These results were contradictory to [16] who reported non-significant effect of seeding depth on the

spike length in wheat but he observed maximum spike length when crop was sown at optimum seeding depth with the increase in seeding depth spike length is reduced. For more number of branches per panicle recorded for D₂ might be due to optimum number of productive tillers as a result of which development of panicle was improved causing more appropriation and more number of branches. Greater number of kernels per panicle recorded for D₂. This is because of optimum number of productive tillers as a result of which growth of panicle was improved causing more appropriation and more number of kernels. Higher 1000-kernel weight can be ascribed to optimum number of tillers m⁻², less competition among productive tillers, more filling of starch in grains and better kernel development. Higher grain yield obtained in D₂ can be attributed to better stand establishment, optimum number of panicle bearing tillers m⁻², higher percentage of normal kernels with higher grain weight because at a seeding depth of D₂ plant have stronger root system and there is no shortage of moisture and nutrients. Above or below this limit resulted in reduction the yield potential probably due to lack of appropriate balance between assimilates supply and number of spikelet per unit area. At shallow seeding depth kernel yield was reduced it could be due to low moisture content at top layer of soil because it is dried quickly. Rebetkze *et al.* [13] who reported that roots of plants sown at 3 cm sought out moisture deeper in the soil profile because the top soil layer is assumed to have dried out very quickly that ultimately results in better growth and development and results in higher yield. Higher straw yield recorded at 3 cm could be attributed to maximum plant population because of better stand establishment m⁻² throughout the growing period and contributed to final straw yield as compared to rest of the treatments. Roy *et al.* [17] reported that maximum straw yield was obtained at an optimum seeding depth which was 4 cm in wheat crop. Higher number of panicle bearing tillers m⁻² and normal kernels with higher grain weight produced higher biological yield when crop was sown at 3 cm depth. Increase in seeding depth than 3 cm reduced the biological yield potential probably due to lack of appropriate balance between assimilates supply and number of spikelet per unit area. We recorded higher harvest index in D₂ treatment due to higher kernel yield in this treatment, which ultimately led to higher values of harvest index.

Regarding kernel quality, higher percentage of sterile spikelets recorded for D₄ was attributed to deep sowing that results in poor root system which caused severe competition for photosynthates at reproductive stage and resulted in high sterility of spikelets particularly at lower location of panicle while, the minimum sterility percentage in D₂ was due to optimum number of panicle bearing tillers, it might be also due to proper root system that provide essential nutrients and causing less sterility. The minimum percentage of opaque kernels recorded for D₂ might be attributed to vigorous and healthy root system, proper availability of moisture and nutrients and better utilization of resources at grain filling stage. Higher percentage of opaque kernels recorded for D₄ was attributed to deep sowing those results in poor root system which caused severe competition for photosynthates at reproductive stage and resulted in high opaqueness of kernels. Higher percentage of abortive kernels recorded for D₄ was due to severe competition for photosynthates at vegetative and

reproductive stage resulted by poor root system and resulted in high abortiveness of spikelets while, the minimum abortive kernels in D₂ was due to better root system, proper availability of moisture and nutrients, optimum number of panicle bearing tillers, and better utilization of resources at grain filling stage. Minimum percentage of chalky kernels recorded for D₂ might be attributed to proper root system, proper availability of moisture and nutrients and optimum plant population which resulted in better utilization of resources at grain filling stage. Whereas, higher percentage of chalky kernels recorded for D₄ was attributed to poor root system that caused severe competition for photosynthates at vegetative and reproductive stage and resulted in high chalkiness of kernels. The higher percentage of normal kernels recorded for D₂. It might be accredited to proper root system, proper availability of moisture and nutrients, optimum plant population, optimum number of panicle bearing tiller, and better utilization of resources at grain filling stage. Lower percentage of normal kernels recorded for D₄ was attributed to poor root system that caused severe competition for photosynthates at vegetative and reproductive stage. Crop plants in these plots were not vigorous and healthy due to unavailability of proper moisture and nutrients. The higher kernel length recorded for D₂ was due to greater source capacity to produce photo-assimilates that were translocated and partitioned into sink. Increase in kernel length may be an outcome of better production environment that imparted better nutrients and water uptake under optimum seeding depth treatment that provide good root system and proper availability of nutrients. Higher kernel water absorption ratio obtained in D₂ which might be due to comparatively more amylase concentration in this treatment. According to the nutritional point of view grain protein content is considered as very important after starch. As now days, all the nations of the world acknowledged about the balance diet. Hence, a good quality rice production is necessary. Higher protein content was recorded when seed were planted at a shallow depth. It might be because of sufficient availability of resources. It was not in case of deep planted rice, where plants remained weak and were unable to attain higher protein contents.

CONCLUSION

Proper seeding depth has an important role in cultivation of direct seeded rice and other crops. According to our study, it is concluded that seeding depth of 3 cm for direct seeded coarse and fine rice is beneficial in terms of better growth, higher yield and improved quality of crop.

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